

ON THE LABOR ACTIVITY OF RURAL WOMEN OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE SILK FIELD

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Abstract: Scientific comments on the labor activity of rural women of Uzbekistan in the field of silk production are presented. Also, in the 30s of the 20th century, it was scientifically analyzed that the use of women's labor in the silk industry is an important issue not only from the point of view of production, but also from a political point of view.

Key words: silk industry, military communism, "Attack" movement, Silk trade, Bolshevik, silk factory

Many reforms were implemented by the Soviet government in the 20s of the 20th century. These reforms were distinguished by their contradictory and complex aspects.

The Soviet policy of "military communism" in 1917 was the first model of the Soviet system, which showed its utter inadequacy, stifling free thinking, work, creativity, and initiative[1]. The introduction of general labor obligation as an important component of the Bolsheviks' policy of "military communism" was also an unexpected emergency for the people of the country. On this basis, the involvement of men and women between the ages of 16 and 55 in the process of forced labor was fully applicable to the women of the local nation, who had not seen the face of the social sphere until that time.

On January 29, 1920, after the government passed the decree "On the procedure of general labor obligation", especially the labor obligation became widespread[2]. In the second half of the 20s of the 20th century, the Bolsheviks, on the basis of their standards, sharply resolved this social and political issue, which included the fate of millions of Turkestan women. The "issue of women and girls" was solved based on the ideology of the existing system. Soon, women's departments started working under the organizations of the Soviet government. In the early years, propaganda was approached very carefully. Wide-scale explanatory work was carried out for women and girls. Also, women's clubs, artels, and shops started working. However, this approach did not satisfy the Soviet government. In order to artificially speed up this process, he began to give it the characteristic of mobilizing force. In September 1926, a council was held by the Central Asian party committees with the participation of women's departments. In it, it was decided to speed up the work being carried out among women and make it mandatory [3]. This mandatory event was called "Attack". That is, priority was given to the policy of solving the women's issue in the style of attack. Special commissions were formed in December 1926 to transfer this company.

The "Offensive" movement of the Soviets made significant progress in 1927-1929. Thousands of women were recruited to work in enterprises, village and district councils, and the judicial system. Many tractor drivers, foremen, collective farm chairmen, club and library directors were trained among them [4]. There has been an increase in activities involving

women and girls in courses to end illiteracy, opening kindergartens and kindergartens for their children.

From 1926-1927, women began to be involved in all areas of production and industry on a large scale. The Soviets decided to use women as a productive labor force, insisting that women had equal rights with men. Women were also involved in agriculture and heavy industry. Also, as a result of such a one-sided policy carried out by the Soviets, conflicts broke out in thousands of families, women's lives were encroached upon. In such cases, the mood of discontent increases in people. Moral values were not taken into account when carrying out the "attack" action[5]. The main goal of the Soviets was to widely involve women in social production. Initially, they were attracted to artels and factories. Later, women were forced to work equally with men in all aspects of production, including heavy lifting, from industry to collective farms [6]. In particular, the involvement of women in heavy industry and agriculture was continuously launched. The silk sector is not left out of these realities. It was observed that the weight of women has increased in the field of silk industry.

From the first years of Soviet power, "Turkipak" paid attention to the widespread involvement of women in the field of cocooning (from the process of revitalizing silkworm seeds to the production of raw materials) [7].

Together with the collective farmers, all their family members were involved in the process of raising silkworms. Similarly, elderly people, elderly women, labor and war invalids, and even teenage children were busy with silkworm care. For example, in 1948, there were 111 workers in the "Stalin" collective farm of the Okhunboboyev district of the Fergana region, 92 in the "Namuna" collective farm, 58 in the "Lenin" collective farm, 50 in the "Yordam" collective farm, and in the "Frunze" collective farm - 35 disabled people were involved in silkworm care [8]. Retired seniors are booked because they are highly skilled in silkworm care. Adolescent children were the main labor force in picking, collecting, transporting and storing mulberry leaves, which are silkworm food.

In 1928-1932, the share of the local population in the composition of the workers of Uzbekistan increased. In particular, their share in the silk industry was 78 percent. It is also observed that the weight of women has increased in the field of silk production. For example, in 1937, the share of women in the silk industry was 58 percent [9].

In the 30s of the 20th century, the use of women's labor in the silk industry was considered an important issue not only from the point of view of production, but also from a political point of view[10]. As a result, women became the main driving force in the silk industry.

In 1938, the total number of workers in the Fergana hairdressing factory was 1466, of whom 461 were men and 1065 were women. Among them, there were 613 workers of Uzbek nationality, 309 of them were men and 304 were women. The number of non-Uzbek workers was 853, of which 152 were men and 701 were women[11]. Due to circumstances such as leave given to working women in connection with the birth of children, the consequences of illness, the composition of workers changed[12]. The workers of Pilakashlik factories were presented with prizes and gifts on the occasion of the holiday. In particular, in 1948, on the occasion of the March 8 holiday, women at the Fergana hairdressing factory were awarded with shirts and women's clothes (skirts) made of sherst[13], and 4 meters of melastin fabrics[15]. Advanced workers were specially recognized in the awards.

Agricultural exhibitions, which are held from time to time, have also been used effectively to establish and promote the silk trade. In particular, "Turkipak" regularly actively participated in traditional agricultural fairs and demonstrated its products. For example, in 1924, demand for silk products was felt in Nizhny Novgorod, and "Turkipak" participated in this fair only with samples of silk products. In 1939, M. Sultonova participated in the All-Union Agricultural Exhibition as one of the well-known farmers. Also, he was awarded with orders and medals for his exhibitions reflecting his exemplary work. At one of these exhibitions, Z. Damirova was awarded the "Za trudovyye otlicheye" medal [16].

Natural silk raw material has retained its popularity regardless of the period. Silk is the lightest and most elastic fabric, it has special advantages because it is shiny and beautiful. These circumstances caused the stability of the population's need for silk fabrics.

Most of the workers in the silk factory in Fergana are women. There were even more women in some industries. For example, it was 64.5 percent in the silk industry[17]. The share of women in the total number of workers was 12.1 percent in 1928-1929, and reached 28.8 percent in 1932, that is, it more than doubled. The increase in the number of female personnel is especially noticeable in industries such as silk production. For example, in the textile industry in 1930-1931, women made up 56 percent of all workers (37 percent in 1928-1929), and in the silk industry, 65 percent (46.3 percent in 1928-1929)[18].

The income of republican collective farms from silk production increased by 22.4% in 1947 compared to 1941[19]. In 1954, Sh.Arabboyeva, the head of the cocooning section of the "Stalin" collective farm, Yangikurgan district, Namangan region, took care of 3 boxes of silkworm seeds for 20 days and gave the state 89.4 kg from each box. handed over a cocoon from And 88.6 kg per box of re-fed silkworm seed. raised cocoons from 500 rubles, 800 kg to Sh. Arabboyeva. wheat and silk cloths were paid for their seasonal labor [20].

However, the conditions in existing factories were not sufficient. For example, many workers suffered from occupational diseases due to the lack of labor protection in the republic's factories. For example, on June 14, 1982, Periya Saytumerova, a worker at the Samarkand cocoon factory, lost 80 percent of her work capacity due to an occupational disease. Therefore, 93 rub. 90 copies. allowance was assigned[21].

The amount of wages and income in cocoon cultivation was much lower than in the industry. The government did not pay attention to the issue of increasing the purchase price of agricultural products, especially cocoons. The Soviet authorities did not fundamentally revise the procedures for payment of wages in the field. Also, many issues related to demographic aspects have been neglected.

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